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IMPACT OF TEACHING EXPERIENCE OF TEACHERS ON THE ACCOMPLISHMENT OF THEIR PROFESSIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES

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IMPACT OF TEACHING EXPERIENCE OF TEACHERS ON THE ACCOMPLISHMENT OF THEIR PROFESSIONAL RESPONSIBILITIES

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impacts of teaching experience on the accomplishment of professional responsibilities among teachers. Teaching experience is a critical factor influencing teachers' effectiveness, classroom management, and student outcomes. This research examines how varying experience levels affect teachers' ability to fulfil their professional duties, including lesson planning, student assessment, and classroom engagement. Data were collected through surveys and interviews with teachers from diverse educational backgrounds and experience levels. The results show that more seasoned educators are better at handling classroom dynamics, modifying their teaching methods, and meeting the demands of a wide range of students. They also demonstrate greater confidence in their academic skills and are more thoughtful about curriculum development. Conversely, novice teachers often face challenges in these areas, requiring extra support and qualified development. The study underscores the importance of continuous professional growth and mentorship programs to enhance the capabilities of less experienced teachers. By fostering a supportive environment, educational institutions can ensure that all teachers, regardless of their experience level, are equipped to meet their professional responsibilities effectively. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on teacher development and highlights the need for targeted interventions to support educators at different stages of their careers.

Keywords: Professionalism, teachers, Academic and professional training, teaching impacts, teaching challenges

Introduction

This study investigates the relationship between teachers' teaching experience and their abilities to fulfil their professional responsibilities. By examining this impact, the study seeks to contribute to existing knowledge and provide understanding for educational stakeholders to improve teacher training programs, professional development initiatives, and policies related to teacher recruitment and retention. This study seeks to shed light on the

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impacts of teaching experience on the accomplishment of professional responsibilities among teachers. By exploring this impact, the study aims to contribute to the field of education and provide valuable insights for improving teaching practices, teacher training, and overall educational outcomes.

Over the years, the education sector has undergone significant changes, including advancements in teaching methodologies, technological integration, and diversification of student needs. Experienced and qualified teachers are expected to be better equipped to adapt to these changes and provide effective instruction, meet diverse learning needs, and maintain a positive classroom environment. However, research on the direct impact of teachers' experience and qualifications on their professional responsibilities is limited. This study aims to bridge this gap in the literature by providing valuable insights into the significance of these factors.

This study's main goal is to determine how teachers' backgrounds and experience affect their capacity to carry out their duties efficiently as professionals. Teachers are tasked with planning teaching programs, implementing programs that have been prepared, and assessing programs after they have been implemented. This study goals to ascertain how teacher qualifications and experience impact student satisfaction. Next, it looks at how a knowledge-intensive culture affects instructional methods, knowledge transfer, and student satisfaction.

As a result, secondary teachers must possess strong intellectual and professional backgrounds. Additionally, it's critical to comprehend the idea of teacher professionalization and the qualities that define a professional teacher before drawing a connection between teacher professionalism and student outcomes. Professionalism in education is a combination of attitudes, behaviour, integrity, and autonomy.

Teachers play a crucial role in the education system, as they are responsible for shaping the minds of future generations. The effectiveness of teachers in fulfilling their professional responsibilities has a direct impact on the quality of education and student outcomes. Understanding the relationship between these factors and the accomplishment of professional responsibilities is essential for improving teaching practices and promoting educational excellence.¹

Teaching experience encompasses a teacher's years in the classroom, working with students from diverse backgrounds and facing various instructional challenges. As teachers gain experience, they acquire valuable knowledge and skills that contribute to their professional growth. They become familiar with effective teaching strategies, develop classroom management techniques, and learn to adapt their instructional practices to meet the needs of different learners. Additionally, experienced teachers often serve as mentors for novice educators, further enhancing the overall quality of instruction within schools.²

The impact of teaching experience in accomplishing professional responsibilities has been a subject of interest for researchers and policymakers in the field of education. However,

there is a need for further exploration and empirical evidence to better understand the impact of these factors on teacher effectiveness.³

Teachers as leaders direct and control themselves, their students, and the community where they work so that they can direct, supervise, regulate, control, and participate in the programs implemented. Based on the above background, it is important to discuss the duties and responsibilities of teachers.⁴

The role that a teacher attaches to himself or that is attributed to him by his environment is one of the crucial components on which they build their professional identity, according to authors who have studied these areas.⁵

Objective of the study

1. To identify the impact of Teachers' teaching experience on the accomplishment of their professional responsibilities.
2. To identify the impact of teachers' qualifications on their ability and professional responsibilities.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of Teachers' teaching experience on the accomplishment of their professional responsibilities?
2. What is the impact of teachers' qualifications on their ability and professional responsibilities?

Significance of the Study

Study will be significant for implications for the field of education and the improvement of teacher professionalism and impact between teachers' teaching experience, and their effectiveness in fulfilling professional responsibilities. Study aims to provide valuable insights to various stakeholders. Educational institutions can benefit from the findings by identifying areas where additional support or resources are needed to enhance teacher performance. Ultimately, this study is comprehensive and the potential to improve student outcomes by enhancing the quality of teaching and learning in educational setups.

Delimitations of the study

1. Islamabad Model Colleges for Boys (IMCB)
2. Islamabad Model Colleges for Girls (IMCG)
3. Male Female Teachers of (IMCB&G)

Literature Review

Many professionals acknowledge the value of years of experience in human resource strategy, including pay scales, benefits packages, and promotion choices. The underlying idea is that when experience is gained through time, it enhances workers' knowledge, skills, and productivity.

The context of this study is within the field of education, specifically focusing on the professional responsibilities of teachers. In many educational systems, teachers are expected to fulfill various duties and responsibilities beyond delivering curriculum content, such as

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managing classrooms, assessing student progress, and supporting student development. This study seeks to examine the impact of teachers' teaching experience and qualifications on their ability to effectively meet these professional responsibilities.

The study acknowledges the importance of experienced and qualified teachers in promoting effective teaching practices and enhancing student outcomes. It recognizes that teaching experience can provide valuable insights and practical knowledge that contribute to effective classroom management and instructional strategies. Furthermore, the study acknowledges the significance of teachers' qualifications, including their educational background, subject matter expertise, and professional development, in equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to fulfill their responsibilities.

Teaching Experience

A teacher's tenure in the classroom is referred to as their teaching experience. It begins on the day a teacher enters the field of teaching. The methods used and the teaching abilities are enhanced through experience. Teachers gain expertise in their fields through time and develop their teaching skills through practical application. Additionally, the disparity in teacher salaries is mostly explained by teaching experience. A study was calculated that additional costs for teaching experience amount to 17 percent (on average) of teacher salaries. All sorts of teachers in Pakistan receive a pay increase each year. Similarly, a teacher's compensation was increased by fifteen increments if he or she had fifteen years of experience in the classroom. Likewise, a teacher's compensation was increased by fifteen increments if he or she had fifteen years of experience in the classroom. In this approach, the experienced teachers are compensated well.⁶

Teaching Experience

The conclusion is that Experience is still important, even in the second decade of teaching and beyond. Does teaching experience make teachers more productive?, The common refrain that teaching experience does not matter after the first few years in the classroom is no longer supported by the power of research. We find that the amount of teaching experience a teacher has over the course of their career is often positively connected with student success increases. Kini and Podolsky's analysis of 30 studies from the past 15 years reveals the following.⁷

1. The first five years of teaching are when changes in a teacher's effectiveness are most obvious, but they continue to increase during the second and frequently third decade of a profession.
2. Students' academic gains are not the only advantage as teachers advance in experience. Attendance at school also gets better.
3. Teachers need to be a part of a supportive and collaborative school environment in order to be effective at any stage of their careers. Another important factor is consistency in teaching duties. The same grade level, subject, or district is where experienced teachers perform at their best.

4. More experienced teachers support increased learning for their pupils, their peers, and the institution as a whole. Working with more experienced coworkers is extremely beneficial for novice instructors.

Quality Learning at School

When all types of students were present in school classes, the lecture and tutorial seemed to function just fine. The increasingly radical changes in the tertiary sector have altered the school landscape, but not entirely in a way that is detrimental to the quality of instruction. Schools must raise the caliber of their instruction because student fees now make up a significant portion of their funding. Many people are doing this by using constructive alignment.

Teaching According to Students Learning

The definition of teaching influences how well we do it. There are three distinct ways to approach teaching. The first is concerned with a learner and the second to the teacher. Effective instruction encourages pupils to use the learning strategies and most likely to produce the desired results. To do this, you'll need to have some understanding of how students learn. Students may choose to learn superficially by engaging in low-level or inappropriate activities, or deeply by engaging in high-level activities that are appropriate for achieving the desired outcomes. Effective teaching encourages the right learning activities and discourages the wrong ones.⁸

Responsibilities of Teacher

Teachers and educators have a duty to engage the community to participate in education in their locality in addition to teaching in various schools and advancing the field of education. Professional educators will be in charge of duties that call for applying knowledge of both materials and procedures. The professionalism of teachers is demonstrated by how well they carry out their responsibilities. Professional teachers are capable of juggling their responsibilities as employees, parents, and citizens of their societies, countries, and religions.⁹

Research Design

Quantitative approach was used in this study and research design was descriptive. Survey method was used. The researcher has presented the regression analysis of the data collected for predicting the influence of Independent Variable on Dependent Variable. The male and female teachers of the Model School & Colleges of Islamabad was population. A total of 518 teachers, including the lecturers, assistant professor, associate professor & professor were sample and total population was 1300. Sample size was 10% of the total population, which was determined via random sampling. The study's sample was made up of a total of 65 randomly chosen male and female teachers.

Data collection

Data was collected through a self-developed questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered to the respective respondents. 5 point likert scale was used in the questionnaire. There are four component of questionnaire i.e. 1st component is related with

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subject matter & knowledge, 2nd is related with instructional knowledge & practice, 3rd is about Assessment and 4th is related with continuous professional development & code of ethics.

Data Analysis

After tabulating the data, SPSS version 25 was used to examine and evaluate each questionnaire item before calculating the results. The descriptive statistics and regression analysis was used. Standard deviations and mean was also used to analyze data on qualities of teachers teaching experience in Islamabad Model Colleges for Boys & Islamabad Model Colleges for Girls.

Results and Discussion

The conclusions and results of the data collected from the respondents serve as the foundation for this chapter. Analysis, interpretation, and discussion of the quantitative and qualitative data gathered by questionnaires deals with the examination of descriptive and regression analysis. One by one, the questionnaires were examined, and then the statistical findings were explained. The function of teaching experience and qualification on teachers' professional responsibilities was predicted using regression analysis. Professionalism of teachers, such as how smoothly a lesson plan proceeds, the growth of pedagogical expertise, and relationships with qualifications, are dependent variables of professional responsibilities of teachers.

The study revealed Teachers with more years of experience demonstrated a higher level of competence in meeting their professional obligations. As teachers gain experience, they develop a deeper understanding of pedagogy, classroom management, and student needs, which positively impacts their ability to fulfill their professional responsibilities.

Table 1: Respondent Experience

Experience	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
10 & above	485	93.6	93.6
7-9	14	2.7	96.3
4-6	15	2.9	99.2
1-3	4	.8	100.0
Total	518	100.0	

Table shows that there is in between 1-3 years of respondent 4 (0.8 %), 4-6 years is 15 (99.2 %), 7-9 years is 14 (96.3 %) and 10 & above years is 485 (93.6 %). 10 & above years is 485 (93.6 %) High average respondent whereas low average is 1.3 years is 4 (0.8 %).

Table 2: Respondent Designation

Designation	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Lecturer	240	46.3	46.3
Assistant Professor	187	36.1	82.4
Associate Professor	85	16.4	98.8
Professor	6	1.2	100.0
Total	518	100.0	

Table shows that lecturer are 240 (46.3 %), Assistant professor is 187 (82.4 %), Associate professor is 85 (98.8 %) and Professor is 6 (1.2 %). Low respondent belong to Professor is 6 (1.2 %) whereas the high respondent are Lecturer 240 (46.3 %).

Table 3: Respondent Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
21-35	47	9.1	9.1
36-50	410	79.2	88.2
51-65	61	11.8	100.0
Total	518	100.0	

Table shows that respondents between 21-35 years age are 47 (9.1 %), 36-50 years are 410, (88.2 %), and 51-65 years are 61 (11.8 %).

Table 4: Regression analysis by teaching Experience

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.044 ^a	.002	.000	7.53249

Table summarizes the results of the regression analysis. The overall regression model summary suggests that teaching experience has a negative relationship with the accomplishment of professional responsibilities. The coefficient value of -7.532 indicates that, on average, for every unit increase in teaching experience, the percentage score in indicators like continuous professional development and code of ethics decreases by 7.532

Table 5: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	56.839	1	56.839	1.002	.317 ^b
	Residual	29277.037	516	56.738		
	Total	29333.876	517			

The ANOVA result, with a value of .317, indicates the overall significance of the regression model. In this case, the p-value is .317, which suggests that the relationship between teaching experience and accomplishment of professional responsibilities is not statistically significant at the conventional significance level of 0.05. However, it is worth noting that the p-value is close to 0.05, which means that the relationship may still have some practical importance or be marginally significant depending on the specific context

Table 6: Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	105.263	.883		119.204	.000
	Teaching Experience	-.739	.739	-.044	-1.001	.317

In conclusion, based on the regression analysis, the impact between teaching experience and the accomplishment of professional responsibilities in the education field is insignificant. Overall, based on the given information, the regression analysis suggests that

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there is no statistically significant impact between teacher qualification and the accomplishment of their professional responsibilities.

Table 7: Teachers' professionalism score in regard to experience

Years of Experience	n	Mean	SD	T-value
10 & above	485	87.5739	5.42093	.027
7-9 years	14	88.0952	4.27960	.071
4-6 years	15	85.1111	4.85777	.127
1-3 years	4	80.8333	8.76652	.068

Table shows that, teachers with greater or less experience have equal score on professionalism. The term "professionalism" in this context refers to the behaviors, attitudes, and qualities that are expected of a teacher in their role as an educator.

Findings

The findings of the study are that most respondents strongly agreed that the high teaching experience and less experience are the same. The data indicates that for teachers with 10 years and above teaching experience, the mean score for the subject matter and knowledge is (87.5739), with a standard deviation of (5.42093). This suggests a relatively high level of expertise and familiarity with the subjects they teach. In terms of instructional knowledge and practice, teachers with 10 years and above of experience have a mean score of (88.4536), with a standard deviation of (7.77410). This indicates a strong understanding of effective teaching methods and pedagogical strategies. These teachers are likely to possess a wealth of experience in delivering instruction and managing classroom dynamics. Regarding assessment, teachers with 10 years and above of experience have a mean score of (86.0687), with a standard deviation of (8.54066) is the main reason that the no influence on teaching experience on the accomplishment of their professional responsibilities.

There is no significant difference in the professionalism of teachers with experience of up to ten years and above and teachers with experience of less than ten years. As a result, professionalism is not necessarily correlated with experience. The findings indicate that having experience as a teacher does not guarantee that one is a professional, hence there was no discernible difference between teachers with different levels of experience.

The study examined various aspects of professionalism, such as adherence to ethical standards, maintaining appropriate boundaries with students, effective communication with colleagues and parents, commitment to professional development, and overall dedication to the teaching profession. Researchers evaluated these criteria through observations, self-assessments, and feedback from colleagues, students, and parents.

Findings are specific to the aspect of professionalism and do not necessarily reflect other aspects of teaching, such as instructional skills, subject matter expertise, or classroom management. Experience may still play a significant role in these areas, as teachers often acquire valuable knowledge and strategies over time.

The study's results suggest that professionalism is not solely dependent on the number of years spent by a teacher in his field. Factors such as personal qualities, dedication to professional growth, and adherence to ethical standards appear to be more influential in determining professionalism. These findings highlight the importance of ongoing professional development and the cultivation of a strong professional ethos, regardless of experience level, in promoting effective teaching practices.

Conclusion

The professionalism of a teacher is a great standard that cannot be overlooked. It give globalization's influence on society as a whole. In order to prove its validity and enable generalisation of the demonstrated qualities to a similar population, the professionalism measurement tool underwent several trials. In light of the major findings, it has been concluded that, there is no impact of teaching experience on the accomplishment of professional responsibilities of teachers. Experienced and less experienced teachers both demonstrated a higher level of competence in areas such as pedagogy, classroom management, and student engagement. Furthermore, Teachers held their perceptions regarding the impact of teaching experience and qualifications.

Recommendations

1. Education policymakers to know and design professional development programs, certification requirements, and career advancement pathways that align with the relationship between experience, qualifications, and professional responsibilities.
2. It is an essential need for educational institutions and policymakers to provide support and resources for teachers' professional development throughout their careers.
3. Collaboration, mentorship programs, and ongoing training opportunities should be emphasized to foster continuous growth. It is essential to acknowledge the limitations of this study, such as the reliance on self-report measures and the potential for subjectivity in teachers' perceptions.
4. Expand the study's sample to include teachers from various grade levels, subjects, and school types. This will enhance the generalizability of the findings and provide a broader perspective on how experience and qualifications influence different educational contexts.
5. Investigate how experience and qualifications influence teacher burnout rates and job satisfaction. Assess whether experienced and highly qualified teachers experience lower levels of burnout and higher job satisfaction due to their enhanced skills and expertise.

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